

Stormwater reuse for agriculture

Deliverable 2.7

Stormwater reuse for agriculture

Deliverable 2.7

Summary

Living lab Flanders is confronted with challenges such as floods, insufficient groundwater replenishment, water shortages in agriculture and lack of availability of conventional resources, all originating in climate change and extreme water stress caused by a high population density and related pavement rates. At the demonstration site in Mechelen, these challenges are integrated through smart control of a flood prevention buffer basin, allowing for both groundwater replenishment and reduction of irrigation needs.

Deliverable number	Work package
D2.7	WP2
Lead beneficiary	Milestone authors
AQUA	Sander Bombeke (PSKW) Joris De Nies (PSKW) Ingeborg Joris (VITO) Stefan Kroll (AQF) Birte Raes (AQF) Frie Van Bauwel (VITO) Gökben Üner (Stad Mechelen) Arnout Ruelens (Stad Mechelen)
Quality assurance	
Ruud Bartholomeus	
Planned delivery date	Actual delivery date
31/05/2024	31/07/2024
Dissemination level	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> PU = Public <input type="checkbox"/> PP = Restricted to other programme participants <input type="checkbox"/> RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium. Please specify: _____ <input type="checkbox"/> CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium

Table of contents

1	Introduction	9
2	Review of the Current State of Technology in The Market	11
2.1	Stormwater control system	11
2.2	Water quality of urban run-off	11
2.3	Sand filtration	12
2.4	(Sub)irrigation	12
3	Technology description at case study	14
3.1	Adapted stormwater buffer tank	14
3.2	Stormwater control system	16
3.3	Sand filtration treatment	17
3.4	Infiltration system	18
3.5	Infiltration control	19
4	Demonstration Phase	22
4.1	Performance storm water control system	22
4.2	Water quality and treatment efficiency	23
4.2.1	Suspended solids	27
4.2.2	Iron	28
4.2.3	Nutrients	29
4.2.4	Salts	31
4.2.5	PAH and mineral oils	31
4.2.6	Other pollutants	32
4.2.7	Conclusion	33
4.3	Performance and effects of infiltration	34
4.4	Performance of the infiltration control	35
5	Challenges and boundary conditions	37
5.1	Business model	37
5.2	Ownership	38
5.3	Stakeholder involvement	39
5.4	Water quality monitoring	40
6	Conclusion	42
7	References	44
	Annexes	47

List of Figures

Figure 1: Schematic overview of the double functionality of subirrigation.	13
Figure 2: Layout of the demonstration site in Mechelen.	15
Figure 3: Concentration of Ammonia in the Run-off water before and after adaptations to the sewer network.	16
Figure 4: Summary of the decision tree incorporated in the subirrigation control.	20
Figure 5: An overview of the Grafana dashboard used to monitor the subirrigation control.	21
Figure 6: Example of the stormwater control concept: operation of the sluice gate based on monitored tank water level and rainfall forecast data.	23
Figure 7: Concentration of suspended solids before and after sand filtration and removal by sand filtration.	27
Figure 8: Concentration of iron before and after sand filtration and removal by sand filtration.	28
Figure 9: Concentrations of orthophosphate, nitrate and nitrite before and after the sand filtration.	30
Figure 10: Concentration profile of chloride in the run-off water through time.	31
Figure 11: Suspect screening in Mechelen, compared with run-off water from another location.	33

List of Tables

Table 1: Technical details of the sand filtration unit.....	17
Table 2: Overview of the samples taken, including the location (green) and the analysis included (blue).	24
Table 3: Mean and maximum concentrations of various pollutants analyzed in the stormwater and the outlet of the sand filter.	47
Table 4: Compounds to be measured yearly	52

History of Changes

Version	Date	Changes and Comments	Section of implemented changes
1.0	31/07/2024	Submission	-
2.0	23/10/2024	History of changes was added to the document	History of changes
		Recommendations on water quality monitoring were added	Section 5.4
		Table with compounds to be monitored for Managed Aquifer Recharge according to VLAREM~II was added	Annex 2
		Conclusion was revised to reflect the changes in the report	Section 6
		Reference to VLAREM~II was added	References
		Table of Content and List of Tables were adapted to reflect the revisions	Table of Content; List of Tables
		Logo's in the header were adapted	-
		Spacing of the references was adapted	References
3.0	04/02/2025	Formatting of the List of Figures and the List of Tables were adapted	List of Figures; List of Tables

List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

CEC Contaminants of emerging concern

EC European Commission

EQS Environmental Quality Standard

EU European Union

LL Living Lab

M Month

PAH Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons

PFAS Per/Poly Fluorinated Alkyl Substances

SF Sand Filtration

WP Work Package

MWWTP Municipal Wastewater Treatment Plant

Executive summary

Living lab Flanders is confronted with challenges such as floods, insufficient groundwater replenishment, water shortages in agriculture and lack of availability of conventional resources, all originating in climate change and extreme water stress caused by a high population density and related pavement rates. At the demonstration site in Mechelen, these challenges are integrated through smart control of a flood prevention buffer basin, allowing for both groundwater replenishment and reduction of irrigation needs.

The demonstration site employs a smart control of the buffer basin based on weather predictions to optimize stormwater retention. The water level in the basin is kept on a predefined setting and emptied based on a cloud control algorithm incorporating predicted rainfall volume in a 6-hour forecast window. Local fallback settings on an edge device are implemented in case the connection with the cloud is lost. The control has been operational for some months and no uncontrolled overflows occurred. The retained water is intended to be used in a subirrigation system in the nearby agricultural fields. In wet conditions, the system operates as conventional drainage, while in dry conditions, it functions as infiltration pipes for stormwater. This dual functionality allows for both excess water drainage and irrigation while increasing the resilience of the local water system, benefiting crops and the local ecosystem. Due to wet weather conditions in 2024, no relevant effect on the agricultural fields could yet be shown. However, based on a previous demonstration within the project, the potential for high infiltration rates and clear improvement of crop growth and quality can be expected. The subirrigation system is remotely controlled, automatically regulating actuators, pumps and valves based on sensors installed in the field and a decision tree optimizing usage of the retained water and distribution across the fields. The buffer control and the subirrigation have intercommunication, allowing to align the flood prevention and the reuse function. Although run-off water is legally considered unpolluted, water quality monitoring in the project uncovered some points of attention for the application for subirrigation. The major anticipated challenge is clogging of the drainage network, so this should be closely monitored in the coming years.

Integrating smart stormwater management and subirrigation systems at the Mechelen demonstration site offers an innovative solution to simultaneously address water scarcity issues and flood management in Flanders. By enhancing groundwater recharge, optimizing stormwater use, and adapting drainage systems, these technologies contribute to a more resilient agricultural sector and ecosystem. Challenges still to be solved are clarity on the required quality, a solid business model and a structure to regulate responsibilities. However, the successful operation and promising results underscore the potential for broader implementation of these solutions to effectively mitigate water scarcity and manage flood risks.

1 Introduction

In 2019 Belgium was ranked 18th in the national water stress rankings from the World Resources Institute, in Europe only preceded by Cyprus (ranked 2nd) and San Marino (ranked 17th) (Kuzma et al., 2023). Belgium is categorized as a country with “Extreme water stress”, indicating it is using more than 80 % of its supply. The main reason is the high population density resulting in a high water demand and the related high pavement rate causing limited groundwater recharge. The imbalance between water supply and demand makes Belgium very sensitive to climate change. Groundwater recharge is even more threatened and sudden demand increases during periods of drought cannot be met.

One of the sectors impacted by water stress and climate change is agriculture. The droughts in 2017, 2018, 2019, 2020 and 2022 were officially recognized as agricultural disasters (Vlaanderen, s.d.). When groundwater levels drop, crop roots can no longer draw it in, and irrigation is required to maintain crops. Water demand of the agricultural sector increases but due to the water scarcity, access to conventional sources such as surface water and groundwater is limited. The agricultural sector takes measures to reduce their dependency on conventional sources by taking water saving measures and collecting run-off from their own areas. But if this is insufficient to meet the water demand, additional resources are needed. Rainwater harvesting is an interesting option and there is interest to exploit run-off from public domain.

Groundwater replenishment is crucial for addressing Belgium's water scarcity problem and for managing irrigation needs in agriculture. Currently, most agricultural fields in Flanders are equipped with tile drainage systems to allow field access by machinery. However, these systems are installed to prevent waterlogging, but are also responsible for draining valuable groundwater into watercourses, even when field access is not required (Willems, 2023). Addressing the issue of uncontrolled discharge by drainage systems can significantly enhance the robustness of the groundwater system. Conventional systems can be converted to level-controlled systems (regulating discharge) or subirrigation systems (allowing irrigation and eventually recharge) (de Wit et al., 2022; de Wit et al., 2024). These systems are gaining popularity in Flanders (Elsen et al., 2020).

Drought is not the only consequence of climate change, also rainfall intensity is expected to increase. With a pavement rate of 16 %, Flanders is very prone to floods caused by urban run-off that cannot be evacuated by the sewer system or the surface water system, which is highly disturbed by the embankment and straightening of rivers (Willems, 2023). Local infiltration of rainwater is increasingly encouraged for citizens and industry. However, this is currently not sufficient to adequately reduce run-off. To prevent floods, a high amount of buffer basins are installed all over Flanders. These basins store water for a short period of time and provide a delayed discharge making it impossible to adequately infiltrate it or to take any other advantage of the water. They are often dimensioned to accommodate a once-in-20-year water peak, causing them to be empty most of the time with their storage capacity largely underutilized.

At the demonstration site in Mechelen, all of these challenges are integrated, and complementarity of infrastructure is sought. Smart control of the buffer basin allows to exploit its storage capacity. Retaining the run-off water allows in to infiltrate and replenish groundwater. Using the drainage

system for subirrigation increases the infiltration area, increasing the potential infiltration rate, increasing the robustness of the water content in the soil at the local agricultural fields and give crops the opportunity to utilize part of the water and reduce irrigation need.

In this report the different aspects of the proposed solution are addressed in depth. Chapter 2 gives an overview of the current state of the art of Stormwater control systems, legislator aspects of urban runoff, sand filtration treatment and (sub)irrigation systems. In Chapter 3, the concepts of the innovative solutions implemented in Mechelen are described in more detail. This chapter separately addresses the adapted stormwater tank, the tank control, the sand filtration treatment, the subirrigation system and the irrigation control. The actual demonstration and the related technical insights concerning the performance of the tank control, the water quality, the effects of infiltration and the performance of the infiltration control, are covered in Chapter 4. Finally Chapter 5 discusses non-technical aspects such as the business model, the ownership model and stakeholder engagement.

2 Review of the Current State of Technology in The Market

2.1 Stormwater control system

Rainfall is captured on surfaces of streets and roofs and leads to runoff. In a separate system, this rainfall-runoff is collected in storm sewers and conveyed towards the receiving water (Butler and Davies, 2004). As many receiving waters of Flanders have limited capacity with respect to the peak flows typically to be expected at the outlet of storm sewers, the water needs to be buffered in dedicated storm tanks to avoid hydraulically overloading the receiving water (Coördinatiecommissie Integraal Waterbeleid, 2012).

In accordance with the Flemish design guidelines, this buffer infrastructure is dimensioned to withhold the runoff water of rainfall events with a return period of up to 20 years through large tank volumes (Coördinatiecommissie Integraal Waterbeleid, 2012). This entails considerable investments, and at the same time leads to these tanks being only partially filled, or completely empty most of the time. Generally, stormwater tanks are designed as open buffers, permeable at the bottom and the sides to allow infiltration.

The novelty of the here tested control concept lies in the exploitation of this unused storage for water reuse purposes such as irrigation (as demonstrated here) or as a source for industrial process water.

2.2 Water quality of urban run-off

In Flanders, rainwater, originating from run-off from roof, terrace, public road, parking area, etc., is legally considered non-polluted (Titel II van het VLAREM, versie van 03/07/2024, Artikel 1.1.2; Coördinatiecommissie Integraal Waterbeleid, 2024). Legislation stimulates the shift to separated sewer systems and requires choosing a destination according to the following prioritization, both for public administrations and citizens (Titel II van het VLAREM, versie van 03/07/2024, Artikel 4.2.1.3; Coördinatiecommissie Integraal Waterbeleid, 2024):

- reuse
- local infiltration
- buffering and delayed discharge in surface water
- discharge in the sewer system

Despite its legal status as a non-polluted water source, recent studies show that contaminants can be expected in urban run-off (De Buyck et al., 2021). In the case study in Mechelen the water quality is monitored to identify the level of pollution that can be expected in a rural stormwater basin. A sand filtration is provided as a barrier to safeguard the subirrigation application with the water quality initially unknown.

2.3 Sand filtration

A rapid sand filter is used as a safety barrier for water quality. Sand filtration is a commonly applied technique, mainly in wastewater applications, and is at TRL 9. Sand filtration has been applied for stormwater treatment already for many years (Municipal technology branch US EPA, 1999). In Flanders, no public applications using sand filtration for urban run-off treatment are in use yet, neither for reuse, nor for discharge.

Rapid sand filtration is primarily used for the removal of suspended solids. The efficiency varies between 50 % and > 90 %. To improve suspended solids removal and to induce removal of additional contaminants (e.g. COD, BOD, organically bound nitrogen and phosphate, and undissolved metals), the sand filter can be preceded by coagulant addition or aeration (VITO, 2010).

No biological activity is expected in a slow sand filtration. Should extensive biological removal of BOD or nitrogen be required, a slow sand filtration can be used, potentially combined with dosage of a carbon source.

2.4 (Sub)irrigation

Irrigation in Flanders is mainly applied by sprinklers, from micro sprinklers to water cannons. This method of irrigation requires high pressure and discharge. Another often used irrigation technique in horticulture is drip irrigation. Within the B-WaterSmart project, a subirrigation system was installed. For installing this subirrigation, the already present drainage was converted to controlled drainage hereby allowing water to flow into the drainage pipes and infiltrating in the soil. The infiltrated water becomes partially available for evapotranspiration of the plant through capillary rise. The other (major) part leaks to the groundwater. The double functionality of subirrigation, allowing both draining water from and adding water to the system, is visualized in Figure 1. Although using controlled drainage for subirrigation is a new practice in Flanders, the technique is already more frequently implemented in the Netherlands (de Wit et al., 2022).

Water supply controls attached to conventional irrigation systems are known and used in the sector, and using groundwater or buffered rainwater from greenhouses, sheds and other buildings on agricultural land for this water supply is common. To our knowledge, it is however the first time a public buffer basin is directly coupled to a smart controlled (sub)irrigation system. A subirrigation coupled to a steering system was not yet applied in Flanders before the B-WaterSmart project as well.

Figure 1: Schematic overview of the double functionality of subirrigation. Figure adapted from Narain-Ford et al. (2020).

3 Technology description at case study

3.1 Adapted stormwater buffer tank

The otherwise standard storm tank, dimensioned according to Flemish design guidelines, is additionally equipped with a moveable sluice gate (DN400). Standard storm tanks are rather shallow and the need for some water height and the risk for a sludge layer on the bottom might prevent the use of the last 20 - 50 cm of the tank. Therefore, the tank in Mechelen is equipped with a small concrete recess of 1m depth protected with a screen added in one corner of the tank to allow pumping the water and avoid clogging of the pump. The tank is furthermore equipped with an impermeable foil on the sides to minimize infiltration in dry periods. The bottom is still permeable. A mismatch in demand and availability of water can be expected since in dry periods less water will be available and the demand will be higher. The partial impermeability of the basin can help to contain the water as much as possible in periods of high demand.

Initially, there were still diffuse sources of pollution present in the stormwater sewer system, such as roadside ditches with non-connected households and a frequently operating overflow. These were addressed concurrently with the construction of the buffer basin. For example, the overflow was redirected to a second buffer basin. The final layout is shown in Figure 2. The stormwater is collected in Basin 1 (rectangular basin). Excess stormwater is discharged to Basin 2 (triangular basin) either through a controlled sluice or an uncontrolled overflow threshold, which also receives any overflow water. From Basin 2, there is a throttling opening to the watercourse to provide instantaneous discharge, meaning there is no storage in Basin 2. Figure 3 shows the implemented measures clearly improved the water quality for ammonia, an indicator for untreated sewage.

Figure 2: Layout of the demonstration site in Mechelen.

Concentration of Ammonium

Figure 3: Concentration of Ammonia in the Run-off water before and after adaptations to the sewer network.

3.2 Stormwater control system

The amount of water stored in the storm tank is monitored by a water level meter (pressure gauge) connected to a local edge device ([PLCnext Technology | Phoenix Contact](#)) mounted onto the switch board of the control unit of the sluice gate. The current status (opening) of the sluice gate is also captured by the edge device. These data are communicated to the cloud component of the control algorithm through a GPRS/4G wireless uplink via MQTT ([MQTT - The Standard for IoT Messaging](#)). Here, the water level is converted to the corresponding volume currently present in the tank, based on the tank geometry. This information is relayed to the irrigation control module operated by Vito through API calls.

At the same time, the rainfall runoff volume expected for the catchment connected to the storm tank is estimated based on catchment surface area and rainfall forecast data ([One Call API 3.0 - OpenWeatherMap](#)) for a forecast horizon of 6 hours. The volume expected to be evacuated from the tank within the rainfall forecast horizon for irrigation via the water reuse pump is ingested from the irrigation control module operated by VITO via API calls.

The volume currently present in the storm tank, expected irrigation volume and the anticipated rainfall runoff volume are used to estimate the surplus volume exceeding the tank capacity. This surplus volume is then translated into a water level setpoint for the storm tank. The setpoint is sent from the cloud back to the edge device. If the current water level exceeds the desired setpoint, the sluice gate is opened. Otherwise, the gate is closed, subject to a small deadband to avoid oscillations in the control loop and too frequent opening and closing of the gate entailing prohibitively high wear of the gate.

If no setpoint is received by the edge device in time, the gate is set to safe fallback settings, i.e. fully open, to ensure safe operation of the tank under all hydraulic circumstances in case of communication failure. If the cloud receives no edge data in time, Aquafin personnel are alerted via email. As additional failsafe, the overflow crest of the storm tank had been designed to allow for safe operation of the tank even under intense rainfall and unfavorable initial conditions, i.e. complete filling.

Early evaluations of the control concept have shown that it is possible to keep the storm tank filled to overflow crest level for most of the time, indicating high potential for water reuse for long periods of time. Whether this will hold true for the upcoming dryer seasons is still under investigation and will for example depend on losses due to infiltration and evaporation.

3.3 Sand filtration treatment

The sand filter (SF) is designed and delivered by BOSAQ. The installation is controlled through a cloud logging platform, coupled to the pilot's PLC. Using remote access, the user can operate the pilot and visualize its parameters. The sand filter is implemented as a containerized unit, consisting of a composite pressure vessel, filled with 4 layers of medium: a support layer of fine gravel (3 - 5 mm), a medium sand layer (1.7 - 2.5 mm), a fine sand layer (0.4 - 0.8 mm) and a top layer of hydroanthracite. Oxygen is dosed in the feed line by means of a venturi. Optionally, coagulant and carbon source can be dosed in the feed line. The container is equipped with an internal effluent tank to store effluent for backwash. The sand bed is backwashed and rinsed once the pressure drop over the filter reaches a preset value. Table 1 lists the technical details and the initial settings during normal operation (BOSAQ, 2023).

Table 1: Technical details of the sand filtration unit.

Parameter	Value
Vessel volume	1.039 m ³
Filter surface area	0,67 m ²

Nominal flow rate	10 m ³ /h
Surface loading rate at 10 m³/h	14.8 m ³ /m ² /h
EBCT at 10 m³/h	6 min
Backwash volume	3,54 m ³

The sand filtration unit is equipped with the following instrumentation for continuous follow-up:

- Flow transmitter feed flow
- Flow transmitter backwash flow
- Level transmitter backwash tank
- Pressure transmitter feed side
- Pressure transmitter top SF vessel
- Pressure transmitter bottom SF vessel
- Pressure transmitter backwash pressure
- Turbidity transmitter feed
- Turbidity transmitter filtrate
- Temperature transmitter feed

3.4 Infiltration system

After the stormwater is stored and quality is secured, the water is infiltrated into nearby agricultural fields. The subirrigation control explained in more detail below will decide when, how much and where water will infiltrate. The treated and stored water is pumped by a 400 V / 2.2 kW / 3 hp self-priming pump. This pump is capable of delivering 35 m³/h to the fields. This is more than currently generated by the treatment container. The reason is that when the treatment would be proven to be not necessary, water can be infiltrated at maximum rate. The 35 m³/h was based on measurements during the local infiltration experiments in 2022. The pump is controlled by the VITO-software. In the pump house, the pump and valve controls are installed as well as the general circuit board for the infiltration system. The water exiting the pump is divided over 4 pipes in the valve control room. Here, an automatic controlled valve and remote readable water meter is installed on each pipe. From here, the 4 supply pipes go to the connected fields.

In the fields, the drainage was adapted to controlled drainage. A control pit and mechanism were installed at the exit of the drainage system. The mechanism is a remote-controlled actuator connected to a bellow inside a PVC pipe. This pipe sits vertically in the exit pipe of the control pit. Moving the bellow up and down adapts the exit height and therefore the drainage level. When the pipe is at minimum level, the drainage works as conventional drainage. When fully raised, the drainage system is blocked off and no drainage is allowed. The water inlet pipe is connected to the drainage pipes by an inlet pit. This pit serves as a joint between the supply pipe and drainage system and as an inspection pit. The pit lid is situated at least 0.5 m underground to facilitate farming operations. Above ground structures are not wanted in a field and might suffer/cause significant damage to farming equipment.

Because of these adaptations, the drainage pipes gain a double function. They drain excess water to prevent too wet conditions for crop growth and to avoid structural damage to the field when working the land in wet conditions. In other conditions they serve as infiltration pipes for stormwater, with the goal to provide plant roots with water through capillary rise, and additionally raise the groundwater level. This way, agricultural crops can benefit from otherwise lost water. When the crops are not benefitting, the surrounding area does so. Groundwater is recharged and provides water to the local ecosystem.

3.5 Infiltration control

In order to use the buffered stormwater as efficiently as possible, a control system was worked out. Based on a decision tree, this control system determines the amount of water going to which field at a given moment. The control system is triggered every 15 minutes. Following parameters are taken into account in this algorithm: groundwater levels in the fields, precipitation of the last 7 days, temperature, the available volume in the buffer basin, the water level in the control pits, the amount of water flowing to each field, and whether the buffer basin is in need of discharging water to accommodate buffering new incoming runoff. To measure these parameters on site, different sensors were installed, in total there are four water level sensors, two flow meters, and a weather station installed. Information on the amount of water available in the buffer basin and on whether water needs to be discharged, is obtained from the stormwater control system. The data are communicated using LoRa, NBloT, 4G and restAPIs. Next to these measured parameters, some boundary conditions are also taken into account. These boundary conditions are (i) for each field the maximum allowed groundwater level, (ii) the status of participation (in or out) and (iii) the crop type planted on each field. By taking these boundary conditions into account, farmers maintain control on water supply to their field. Figure 4 shows a summary including the most important steps in the decision tree.

Based on the outcome of the decision tree, the infiltration control regulates the pump, the valves on the supply pipes, and the inlet pipe of the drainage using the LoRa, 4G and NBloT network. All measurements and controls are visualized in a Grafana dashboard. An impression of this dashboard is given in Figure 5. Together with some foreseen alarms (e.g. for frost protection), the tool facilitates keeping an overview of the situation on site and verifying whether the controls are operating as expected.

Figure 4: Summary of the decision tree incorporated in the subirrigation control. This decision tree comprises different parts in case there is a risk of freezing (purple), there is a need to evacuate water from the basin (orange), and in case there is water in the basin, but no evacuation is needed (light green-blue). The general part is indicated in grey, and the part where data is exchanged between the subirrigation and the basin control is indicated in bright light blue.

Figure 5: An overview of the Grafana dashboard used to monitor the subirrigation control. The graph titles are translated to English and put on enlarged in grey boxes.

4 Demonstration Phase

4.1 Performance storm water control system

After extensive testing on a pilot system, both the software and hardware of the control system of the storm tank have been successfully operating for several months in full scale. None of the issues that were encountered during this period (mostly sporadic communication failures due to unstable 4G signal or message-broker outages of several minutes to hours) lead to major downtime or erroneous behavior of the control. Sensing, communication, data ingestion, operation of the sluice gate, data visualization and alerting worked as foreseen, leading to the conclusion that the developed concept and applied implementation technologies provide an apt solution for the control objective at hand.

Figure 6 illustrates the successful operation of the storm water control system. Based on the rainfall forecast (top) and the water level in the tank (bottom), a desired setpoint water level (bottom) is calculated. If this is exceeded by the measured water level, the gate opens (mid-section). After the peak of the forecasted rainfall event, the sluice does not need to be operated anymore until a new rainfall event is detected. This reduces the number of required control actions and thus decreases the likelihood of wear of the sluice gate. After the rain event, the tank is filled almost to full capacity, maximizing the water reuse potential.

Figure 6: Example of the stormwater control concept: operation of the sluice gate based on monitored tank water level and rainfall forecast data.

Based on the water level measurements available from the tank, the flow under the opened sluice gate (assuming free outflow) was determined to estimate the cumulated total volume of water diverted towards the receiving water that could have been used for reuse purposes under ideal circumstances (100 % reuse rate). The resulting 50.000 m³ observed over the past four months highlight the high reuse potential for the investigated location subject to further analysis and validation under real-life reuse scenarios. Note that this large volume may be exceptional due to the substantial amount of rainfall in recent months. This significant rainfall also led to saturated soil, making reuse for subirrigation impossible and potentially causing substantial infiltration into the storm tank. In any case, there is a mismatch in water supply and availability when reusing run-off water for (sub)irrigation or another application with the highest demand during dry periods. Therefore the total collected water is not necessarily a good parameter to express reuse potential. For better estimations, long-term monitoring of effectively reused volumes are required, but this was not possible within the current project window. A major aspects of the future research will be the validation of the made assumptions and transferability to other locations and different weather conditions.

4.2 Water quality and treatment efficiency

Table 2 shows an overview of the samples that were taken to assess water quality during the demonstration phase.

Table 2: Overview of the samples taken, including the location (green) and the analysis included (blue). (RWA BA: rain water before adaptations; min oil: mineral oil; nutr + org: nutrients and organic matter related parameters (including suspended solids))

Date	RWA BA	Before SF	After SF	PAHs + min oil	metals	salts	Nutr + org	<i>E.coli</i>	CECs
03/09/2020	X			X	X		X		
24/09/2020	X			X	X		X		
28/09/2020	X			X	X		X		
05/10/2020	X			X	X		X		
14/10/2020	X			X	X	X	X		
21/10/2020	X			X	X	X	X	X	
28/10/2020	X			X	X	X	X	X	
02/11/2020	X			X	X	X	X		
12/11/2020	X			X	X	X	X	X	
01/12/2020	X			X	X	X	X	X	
14/12/2020	X			X	X	X	X	X	
04/01/2021	X			X	X	X	X	X	
18/01/2021	X			X	X	X	X	X	
23/11/2023		X		X	X	X	X		
28/11/2023		X		X	X	X	X		
13/12/2023		X		X	X	X	X		
08/01/2024		X	X	X	X	X	X		
16/01/2024		X	X	X	X	X	X		
19/01/2024		X		X	X	X	X		
22/01/2024		X	X	X	X	X	X		
23/01/2024		X	X	X	X	X	X		
30/01/2024		X	X	X	X	X	X		X
28/02/2024		X	X	X	X	X	X		
12/03/2024		X	X		X	X	X		

19/04/2024		X	X	X	X	X	X		
25/04/2024		X	X	X	X	X	X		
27/05/2024		X	X		X	X	X		

As explained in Section 2.2, urban run-off is legally considered to be clean water. So no legislation applies concerning its quality for reuse. However, since it is clear from literature that urban run-off is not always clean, its quality is compared to some legal frameworks that should be considered when using another non-clean source, such as wastewater treatment effluent.

The required water quality for subirrigation is not clearly defined since it does not fit within the existing legal framework. On the one hand, it is an irrigation method, so protection of the plant and the operators of the network should be taken into account. However, there is no direct contact between the plant and the water and the soil package between the roots and the drains serves as an additional barrier (Narain-Ford et al., 2022; Tang et al. 2023), making legal frameworks for irrigation not entirely applicable.

On the other hand, large ‘leakages’ to the groundwater can be expected, as already mentioned in Section 2.4. Only a minor part of the water will contribute to increased crop transpiration and the rest of the water will infiltrate to the groundwater. This is particularly the case when infiltrating the water at high rates in case of a forced evacuation of the basin preceding a predicted rainfall event. Which share of the water is used by the plants and which share infiltrates to the groundwater strongly depends on the subsurface type and the climatological conditions (de Wit et al., 2024). Protection of the groundwater must be considered, and ground water protection zones and other quality requirements should be taken into account. Therefore, some legal frameworks concerning groundwater recharge are also included in the following. However, in the case of urban run-off, the a pragmatic approach to the legal requirements for infiltration is recommended, keeping in mind the situation without reuse. Water that is infiltrated through the subirrigation system would in any case be stored temporarily in an infiltrating buffer basin, like the default situation where a buffer basin is solely meant for flood prevention and there is no reuse aspect. The bottom of these infiltrating buffer tanks is at about the same depth as the subirrigation drains. Infiltration via the bottom and the sides of the buffer tank would therefore have a similar effect on groundwater compared to infiltration through subirrigation. However, through the subirrigation higher infiltration rates can be achieved, of which the major part will probably reach the groundwater (De Wit et al. 2024). If the groundwater table is below the level of the drains (and therefore also below the bottom of the bufferbasin), the soil package between the drains and the groundwater table can act as a barrier for some compounds.

Because of its unclear legislative framework, the water quality in this case study is compared with several legislative frameworks:

- Environmental quality standard for ground water (Titel II van het VLAREM - bijlagen, versie van 03/07/2024, Bijlage 2.4.1).

- Guidelines for quality of irrigation water from the Agency for Agriculture and Fisheries (Agentschap Landbouw & Zeevisserij, s.d.).
- Minimum requirements for reuse of municipal effluent (Regulation (EU) 2020/741 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 May 2020).
- Recommended values for subirrigation by KWR (de Wit et al., 2023).
- Tipping point fertilizer/water for declaration to the fertilizer database in VLAREME (Adriaens et al., 2022).
- European Drinking water Directive (Directive (EU) 2020/2184 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 December 2020)

A complete overview of the analysis results can be found in Table 3 in Annex 1. Some parameters are highlighted in the following.

4.2.1 Suspended solids

Figure 7 displays the behavior of suspended solids in the system. Suspended solids can cause mechanical blocking of the drainage pipes (de Wit et al., 2023) and can be a carrier for other pollutants.

The EU Guideline 2020/741 concerning irrigation with treated municipal wastewater recommends TSS < 10 mg/L for the most stringent quality class (quality A, when the water is in direct contact with the edible part consumed raw) (Regulation (EU) 2020/741 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 May 2020). The rainwater in the buffer basin contains still quite some suspended solids. The sand filter can achieve a mean removal of about 40 – 50 %, which is less than expected based on literature

Figure 7: Concentration of suspended solids before and after sand filtration and removal by sand filtration. In the graph, the total amount of analysis and the amount of analysis above LOQ (between brackets) are indicated.

(see Section 2.3). The class A-requirement from EU guideline 2020/741 can be met in most cases, the requirement for other quality classes can always be met. Since subirrigation is used, it is not required

to meet class A since there is no direct contact between the edible part of the crop. Subirrigation itself is not part of this particular guideline, but classes B and C, covering drip irrigation, can be used as a guidance.

When subirrigation is applied, there is a risk of mechanical blocking due to solids content. Therefore a very stringent value for suspended solids (TSS < 0.01 mg/L) when applying subirrigation is proposed by KWR (de Wit et al., 2023). This value cannot be met.

4.2.2 Iron

Figure 8 displays the behavior of iron in the system. The water in the buffer basin has a high iron content. Given the high iron content in the groundwater, this iron probably originates from infiltrating groundwater in the sewer pipes, connected street ditches or the basin itself. The measured concentrations are no problem for the EQS for groundwater (Titel II van het VLAREM - bijlagen, versie van 03/07/2024, Bijlage 2.4.1). The guidelines from the Agency for Agriculture and Fisheries

Figure 8: Concentration of iron before and after sand filtration and removal by sand filtration. In the graph, the total amount of analysis and the amount of analysis above LOQ (between brackets) are indicated.

(Agentschap Landbouw & Zeevisserij, s.d.) are slightly exceeded, but as these guidelines are very strict and there is no contact with the aboveground parts of the crop (so no rust precipitation on the crop itself), it is expected that there are no adverse effects on the crops. The high concentrations might however be a problem for the drainage system. As is clear from de Wit et al. (2023), iron precipitation can block the drainage system within a quite short timing. The water already comes into contact with the atmosphere when entering the basin and the treatment unit contains an air venturi to precipitate as much Iron as possible before the sand filtration. The sand filter does remove some of the iron, when it is attached to suspended solids or precipitated e.g. with phosphate, but the removal percentages remain quite low.

4.2.3 Nutrients

Nutrient concentrations in the system are shown in Figure 3 and Figure 9. The phosphorous content exceeds the EQS for groundwater slightly (Titel II van het VLAREM - bijlagen, versie van 03/07/2024, Bijlage 2.4.1).

There is some phosphorus removal by the sand filter. This is assumed to be mainly organic phosphorus, attached to solids that are removed, since the concentration of orthophosphate remains more or less constant. The filter was equipped with a dosing point for coagulant (iron chloride) for further phosphorus removal. This coagulant was not used since the iron concentrations were already high. After treatment, there are still exceedances of the groundwater EQS.

However, the contribution of phosphorus by the infiltrating water to the ecosystem at the agricultural field will probably be minimal. VLM defined the tipping point fertilizer/water for declaration to the fertilizer database as < 2 mg P/L and 15 mg N/L in VLAREME (Adriaens, 2022). It is assumed everything below these concentrations will be negligible in the total application. Nevertheless, given the direct influence of the groundwater system, it is recommended to monitor the impact of the phosphorous on the groundwater quality.

Figure 9: Concentrations of orthophosphate, nitrate and nitrite before and after the sand filtration.

Concerning nitrogen, nitrate concentrations are lower than the EQS for groundwater. Ammonia concentrations have decreased since the adaptations to the sewer network (see Section 3.1). The EQS values are still exceeded, but the measured values are lower than the local background value, which is evaluated as acceptable since no deterioration of local quality is caused. Nitrite concentrations are also exceeding the EQS, however not exceeding the EU drinking water limit (Titel II van het VLAREM - bijlagen, versie van 03/07/2024, Bijlage 2.4.1; Directive (EU) 2020/2184 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 December 2020). Given the direct influence of the groundwater system, it is recommended to monitor the impact of ammonia and nitrite.

4.2.4 Salts

The time dependent concentration of chloride in the run-off water is shown in Figure 10. Chloride concentrations are most of the time below the guideline for irrigation water from the Agency for Agriculture and Fisheries (Agentschap Landbouw & Zeevisserij, s.d.). The use of road salts during periods of freezing weather causes a peak in chloride concentrations. The same can be noticed for sodium and conductivity. The concentrations are quickly reduced to normal when the application of road salts is ended.

The peaks in chloride and EC are comparable to concentrations often found in surface water or reclaimed water. For soil, these concentrations will be no problem. The low concentrations during the rest of the year will result in sufficient flushing. For crops sensitive to salts, the subirrigation can be stopped temporarily if the application of road salts is announced.

Figure 10: Concentration profile of chloride in the run-off water through time.

4.2.5 PAH and mineral oils

PAH's and mineral oils are typical pollutants found in road run-off. In Mechelen these compounds were found in only part of the samples. PAHs never exceeded the EQS for groundwater (Titel II van het VLAREM - bijlagen, versie van 03/07/2024, Bijlage 2.4.1). With mineral oils there was an exceedance in some samples. After sand filtration, no PAH's nor mineral oils were detected. A treatment, such as sand filtration, or a hydrocarbon separator is thus recommended to protect the groundwater system from mineral oils. If not applied, the accumulation of these hydrophobic compounds should be monitored as their removal by the soil microbiome depends on their persistence and mobility (Narain-Ford et al., 2022).

4.2.6 Other pollutants

Microbiological indicators (*E. coli*) were only monitored in the first phase (2020 – 2021), when the rainwater was still polluted by e.g. overflow water. At that point, concentrations as high as 10^4 cfu/100 mL were identified. This is too high to be evaluated as clean water for agricultural irrigation. With the adaptations described in Section 3.1, it is assumed that the presence of *E. coli* was lowered to at least $< 10^3$ cfu/100 mL to meet the criteria of clean water (Agentschap Landbouw & Zeevisserij, s.d.), but it is recommended to verify this again. The current EQS for groundwater concerning microbiological contamination is very strict (0 cfu/100 mL) (Titel II van het VLAREM - bijlagen, versie van 03/07/2024, Bijlage 2.4.1). This will change with the revision of the Flemish groundwater related legislation

To evaluate the presence of contaminants of emerging concern (CECs), a semi-quantitative suspect screening (850 suspects) was performed on the run-off water. More than 70 suspects were identified (Figure 11), which is more compared to another rainwater locations. Pesticides can be expected in run-off water, but the quite significant share of pharmaceuticals is surprising. This might indicate that there is still not a sufficient decoupling from the wastewater and the rainwater system, despite the significant reduction of ammonia that was discussed in Section 3.1. The cause might be wrongly connected households or upstream ditches with non-connected clusters of houses. Further investigation of the rain water sewers and improvements to locate and decouple remaining sources of potential pollution are recommended and are planned in the near future.

The identified suspects were present in concentrations < 0.005 – < 0.1 µg/L. This is below the EU drinking water limit for single pesticides (0.1 µg/L) (Directive (EU) 2020/2184 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 December 2020) and below the EQS of groundwater for single pesticides (0.1 µg/L) (Titel II van het VLAREM - bijlagen, versie van 03/07/2024, Bijlage 2.4.1). The sum of all CECs could not be checked with the maximum sum of all pesticide concentrations in both legal frameworks, since the performed suspect screening was only semi-quantitative. This comparison with relevant legal frameworks indicates that concentrations are rather low and the risk is evaluated as limited. However, given the significant amount of detected CECs, the direct influence on the groundwater system and the differences in behavior for different substances (Narain-Ford et al., 2022), follow-up is recommended.

Figure 11: Suspect screening in Mechelen, compared with run-off water from another location. D0 indicates the samples were analyzed undiluted.

PFAS were not analyzed in this project. The current run-off area and the location of the buffer basin are not situated in a No-Regret-Zone (Agentschap Zorg en Gezondheid, 2022), but it is recommended to do a preventive screening on this in long term set-ups..

4.2.7 Conclusion

According to legislation the run-off water in the case in Mechelen can be considered as non-polluted (Coördinatiecommissie Integraal Waterbeleid, 2024). However, the performed screening identified some points of attention. The most important point of attention is the risk for clogging of the drainage network. Both mechanical blocking (due to suspended solids), chemical fouling (due to iron precipitation) and biological fouling (due to relevant concentrations of nutrients and organics in the water) might occur within a few years when applying subirrigation (de Wit et al., 2023).

Phosphate, ammonia and nitrite exceed current EQS for groundwater (Titel II van het VLAREM - bijlagen, versie van 03/07/2024, Bijlage 2.4.1). However, when evaluated considering fertilizing guidelines and drinking water guidelines respectively, the related risk is considered limited. However, close monitoring is recommended. Additionally, organic micropollutants are a point of attention, mainly indicating that the rainwater sewer does not seem to be completely free of faulty connections.

The sand filtration proved to be useful in removing trace concentrations of PAH's and mineral oil and in reducing the suspended solids and iron content slightly. However significant removal rates could not be achieved. Therefore, it is questionable whether the investment and operational costs of the treatment are justifiable within the overall concept. Other treatment set-ups with better removal rates might be considered. Moreover, good communication with the end user concerning the quality

uncertainties is key. When applying subirrigation, the groundwater system is influenced directly and precautionary measures such as monitoring are proposed. However, as long as there is no clear legal framework, pragmatic evaluation in comparison with other, generally used, water sources and in comparison with other pathways for urban run-off is recommended.

4.3 Performance and effects of infiltration

Since the construction of the basin has finished, the weather has been a challenge, preventing extensively testing of the capabilities of the subirrigation. During the basin construction, a smaller scale on-site simulation was set up, running from month 21 to 26. Results shown are from this on-site simulation. Five locally grown crops were planted on site, with half of them receiving subirrigation through the drainage system, while the other half acted as the control group. The buffer basin was simulated using a water storage container. The experiment aimed to simulate the optimal functioning of the buffer basin for the agricultural reuse of stormwater. Valuable data regarding infiltration speed, groundwater levels, soil moisture, and crop response was gathered. Main results are that infiltration rates go up when groundwater levels drop, which is expected. Infiltration ranged from 35 m³/ha.day to 120 m³/ha.day. The different crops gave variable harvest results when comparing subirrigation to no irrigation during a drought. For example, pumpkins yielded 29 tonnes/ha without and 40 tonnes/ha with subirrigation in 2022. For corn there was no difference. Cabbages yielded the same but differed in quality: 78 % bursted when not irrigated while 50 % bursted when subirrigation was applied. This shows that the irrigation needs were not completely met, but the subirrigation provided substantial drought mitigation.

Figure 11: Cabbages and celeriac do profit from the subirrigation. The growth without subirrigation is displayed on the right and is showing smaller crops of lower quality compared to the growth with subirrigation, displayed on the left.

4.4 Performance of the infiltration control

All separate components of the control system have been tested successfully. Firstly, since the sensor installment, measurements have been carried out without problematic interruptions. Small interruptions were however still present. Most of these smaller interruptions were solved by mounting the communication devices higher to optimize connectivity. There were some issues with the water flow meters due to technical defects which were solved. Second, the data ingestion algorithms and data visualization has been continuously operational since its implementation in February without any problems. Third, the remote control of the different regulated components was tested, and these worked successfully after solving some teething problems. In particular the remote control of the inlet pipe needed tweaking before the input signal caused the bellow to move to the right level. As this was new technology, the need for such tweaking can be foreseen. Lastly, the IT infrastructure developed to continuously control the infiltration system has been continuously operational since its implementation in February.

The initial delay of building the buffer basin and the following (abnormally) wet winter and spring prevented the system from being tested extensively in its entirety. The set of different situations to test if the controls do as is expected remained limited. To overcome this and have more extensive testing within the project timeline, dry run testing of the infiltration control was carried out. During this testing, different scenarios were run to check if the system switches to the expected 'status' without actually sending commands to devices on site. These tests were successful. Moreover, the numbers used for e.g. estimating the amount of water that can be discharged in the system (needed in the algorithm), were estimated from the experiment that was carried out prior to starting the building of the buffer basin which increases our confidence that they represent local conditions.

Although we encountered challenges due to time constraints and the amount of precipitation, demonstrating all different components separately was done successfully, and it was shown during the project that the whole concept is viable. The main challenge encountered during the project regarding the infiltration control that needs improvement when replicating the concept is the "slow" communication protocols selected to send control commands to the devices on site. The IoT communication protocols did not cause difficulties for the measurements, but created constraints on how detailed the infiltration can be controlled. These protocols were chosen because of the more practical implementation, the hardware choice, and the slightly more remote setting of the sensors on the agricultural land, which makes it easier to use low power options. Fine tuning the numbers used in the decision tree should minimize this problem. However, when there is an option to use other, more performant communication protocols and suitable hardware, which make it possible to react to a command at any moment, this would be the preferred option in a replication of the infiltration concept.

5 Challenges and boundary conditions

5.1 Business model

Defining a business model for the solution demonstrated in Mechelen is not easy for multiple reasons. At first, when reusing water, one is working within a framework where there is competition from other water sources such as groundwater, surface water and tap water. In general water, as a fundamental right for all people, is very cheaply priced in Flanders, and therefore not properly appreciated. There is not a lot of margin to work within if one wants to get revenues from selling the water. The fact that there is no 100 % assurance on quality or availability is an extra disadvantage in this view. Secondly, the most important beneficiary in this demonstration is the environment, giving it an important ideological component. The willingness to pay by stakeholders is related to their convictions about the importance of environmental protection. The costs of this water-smart solution can be split into investment costs (CAPEX) and operational costs (OPEX). Both cost types will be considered separately.

CAPEX costs are on the one side the costs for adapting the original buffer basin (i.e. the sluice gate, the concrete recess, the local PLC). In this case, also the decoupling of the overflow can be included in the CAPEX, but this won't always be required. The cost of these adaptations is high for a potential customer, but relatively low compared to the complete cost of installing a buffer tank (+/- 1 %). Given its small share of the cost, it may be for the future to incorporate smart control as a standard at buffer basins. Even if there is no concrete decrease, such a control can help to better manage the basin according to the water flow (e.g. no delayed discharge as long as there is still a high flow). This is rather a policy recommendation and will not help in closing the business case in the near future. Additional CAPEX costs might be present at the reuse side, in this case the treatment and transportation system and the adaptations to the drainage network. Given the ideological component, CAPEX cost are currently often eligible for grants. This can help in finding a solid business case since it only has to deal with operational costs, but it is unclear if grants will remain available for these type of projects in the future. If no grants are available the CAPEX costs will have to be financed by other stakeholders, that will be mentioned in the discussion on OPEX costs. It is key to keep the costs as low as possible and make a careful consideration about what are 'must-haves' and what are 'nice-to-haves'.

To have a sustainable and replicable solution, there must be at least a closed business case for the operational costs. These include maintenance costs of the hardware, electricity costs (for the sluice and the pumping), computational and maintenance costs of the control and potentially costs for treatment and/or quality monitoring. The biggest part of the OPEX costs is independent of the scale of the solution. So, for larger basins, the cost per cubic meter of water will be lower. The end user of the water or, more general, the one that is benefiting from available water at the location of the basin, the is one of the stakeholders that might be willing to contribute. As mentioned, the low price of alternative water sources and the uncertainties about (time of) availability and sometimes quality might be important barriers for this. Especially in this case, where the water is applied through subirrigation. For a farmer, to get the most out of the water, he would rather apply it above ground. By applying it through subirrigation, a large part is leaking to the groundwater and largest beneficiary

is the environment. As the farmer gets an advantage from the water, he will have some willingness to pay, but it is not enough to cover the complete OPEX from this water-smart solution.

The ideological component creates a need for alternative financing models. Stakeholders were consulted during the CoP's (with one CoP dedicated on financing and ownership) and the following financing options were suggested:

- Contribution from the people/municipality with impermeable surfaces leading to extensive run-off in the area (polluter pays principle).
- Increasing the chances of getting a permit (eventually at reduced costs) for groundwater use for who is contributing to groundwater recharge through these kinds of projects. This can be for the farmer, but also for other external stakeholders (industry, ...)
- Making it possible for companies to invest in these projects as part of their CSR strategy (corporate social responsibility)
- Recreative use of the buffer basin (boats, ice-skating...)
- Social use for allotments, CSA picking gardens
- Using the area of the buffer basin for energy production, e.g. through solar panels. This can for example be coupled to a charging point for electrical vehicles
- Make the area around the buffer basin available for advertising (railway and biking/walking route passing nearby)

In the case of Mechelen, mobilizing private resources seems the most promising, given the proximity of two industrial areas. In the coming months these financing options will be further explored.

5.2 Ownership

Next to arranging the financial part, also practical and legal agreements between the different stakeholders are key for a sustainable implementation. The ownership has multiple aspects.

At first there is the aspect of hardware maintenance. Responsibility boundaries within the system should be aligned and agreements on intervention should be made. In Mechelen there is some extra complexity for the part of the basin itself, since during the construction of the basin, the daily management of the sewer system has changed responsibilities, and the ownership of the software is not in the same hands as the ownership of the corresponding software.

At second there is the aspect of water quality. During the project, a sand filtration treatment was installed but as was clear from Section 4.2, the added value is limited and not all water quality parameters could be lowered to the most ideal values. Moreover, the water in the basin originates from urban run-off. Street drains are openly accessible and undesirable discharges cannot be 100% excluded. Efforts can be made to educate and raise awareness among citizens. Adding sensors or do regular monitoring can provide information. However, all these measures come with an additional cost, which is not desirable as is clear from section 5.1. Moreover, they will never provide a complete assurance. This does not need to be insurmountable. When using surface water, the end user also does not have complete control over the intake quality. But good communication, expectation management and agreements between stakeholders are key.

At third, there is a need for redirecting the revenue streams to the different cost items and bringing the business plan into practice.

A suitable form of cooperation needs to be identified, to arrange the three aforementioned aspects together with all other practical and administrative arrangements. This aspect was also discussed with the stakeholders during the CoP. Similar roles of different stakeholders prevent one of the stakeholders from assuming full management. Given the lack of an integral water company in Flanders, other solutions were explored. Establishing a cooperative was ruled out, given the small scale of the case. Already existing local organizations (possibly in cooperation with municipality) were considered, such as a neighborhood committee, rural guild, nature associations, etc.

5.3 Stakeholder involvement

Acquiring funds, support and agreements requires good relations between stakeholders. Within the duration of the project, the project partners raised support of local citizens, farmers and companies while also communicating and discussing with governmental agencies and researchers. Stakeholder involvement goes further than having relations between directly involved partners. Society, government, industry and academia must be involved somehow to have a fully supported concept.

Besides local government, the local farmers and citizens are key stakeholders. The basin is constructed to prevent flooding damage for local citizens. Upon informing the direct neighbors of the project and its goal, their reactions were positive. This was a crucial step since they could slow down construction by filing a complaint against permissions. The local community was informed of the project during on-site events, raising support and awareness. Several press moments were held at the start of the basin construction and during its opening.

Next to the local citizens, the farmers are essential stakeholders for the reuse success. They provide land and infrastructure with which the subirrigation of excess water is possible. They double as user and provider. In dry periods they profit from the irrigated water. At the end of or before their cropping season they provide means to solve flooding problems in a more sustainable way. Because of the small size of the basin only a few neighboring farmers could join in. There is interest in a larger storage volume in the basin from the farmer's side.

Researchers and governmental agencies also have shown interest in the concept of the Hombeek case. External parties from those sectors were informed about the progress and development of the project and gave valuable input in discussions about (among other things): possible current and future challenges, replication viability, beneficial changes, ... It is important to be able to test ideas against the knowledge and experience of others, certainly regarding possible policy changes and academical developments. Stakeholders from industrial sectors might become essential stakeholders for financing purposes in this specific case. They might also be important end-users of the reuse water if the concept is replicated elsewhere. Valuable lessons can be learned from other projects applying subirrigation, such as the demonstration in Kinrooi (Elsen et al., 2020) and the several demonstrations in the Netherlands (de Wit et al., 2023). These demonstrations use MWWTP effluent instead of urban runoff as a water source for subirrigation. However, the effect of subirrigation on crop development and

the water system and the investigation of quality concerns can provide useful insights. Therefore these cases are often referred to in this report.

5.4 Water quality monitoring

To ensure the use of the buffered water in the subirrigation does not contaminate the groundwater on the longer term, a monitoring protocol is needed. As stated above (**§Fout! Verwijzingsbron niet gevonden.**), a clear legal framework for the particular situation at Hombeek does not exist. However, as of 21/6/2024, a new legislation concerning groundwater was approved by the Flemish government (Titel II van het VLAREM, Hoofdstuk 5.54, Art. 5.54.4, versie van 06/10/2024). This legislation includes clear guidelines on water quality monitoring for Managed Aquifer Recharge (MAR). It requires yearly measurements of the compounds listed in Table 4 in Annex 2 as well as 3-monthly measurements of pH, electrical conductivity and temperature. Even though strictly speaking, the set-up in Hombeek does not fall under this legislation, the situation is similar enough due to the “leakage” to the groundwater to use the new legislation as a guideline for the selection of relevant parameters and monitoring frequencies.

To apply this legislation in a relevant way to the case in Hombeek, the quality results from the monitoring campaign conducted during the demonstration (see Section 4.2) lead to insights into relevant parameters to follow up in the future. Based on this monitoring campaign and the monitoring proposed in the legislation mentioned above, the following monitoring actions are recommended in case of long-term application:

- Yearly visual inspection of the subirrigation system on signs of clogging is recommended, such as iron precipitation and infiltration speed.
- The monitoring demonstrated risks related to phosphate, ammonia and nitrite and the occurrence of CEC's that might indicate faulty connections. Yearly monitoring of these parameters is recommended both in the applied run-off water and in the surrounding groundwater. A decrease in time of these parameters should be observed if measures are taken to solve faulty connections.
- Typical contaminants in urban run-off such as PAH's, mineral oils and metals were not detected in problematic concentrations after sand filtration. Future monitoring is not necessarily recommended. However, if no sand filtration is applied, yearly monitoring of PAH's and mineral oils in the run-off water is recommended.
- Application of road salts in winter will increase conductivity. If budget is available, the installation of a conductivity sensor in the buffer basin is recommended to automatically stop reuse activities if a conductivity increase is occurring. Alternatively, good communication with the municipality about the application of road salts or no reuse at all in periods of frost are potential cheaper measures.
- The presence of PFAS was not tested during the project as there is no indication for their presence. If long term reuse at the agricultural field is planned, a one-time screening of the run-off water is recommended.

Even though this forms a reasonable approach from safety perspective, the costs of this monitoring need to be taken into account when further looking into the business case.

6 Conclusion

Within the B-WaterSmart project, a buffer basin was built in Mechelen. This basin is managed in an innovative way: The buffer basin itself is adapted such that buffered water is retained as long as possible. This facilitates the possibility of stormwater reuse. In this case, a smart subirrigation system is coupled to the buffer basin. The reused water is hence used to irrigate crops, it can also be expected that a significant part of the water will leak to the groundwater and thus contributes to groundwater recharge.

During the demonstration phase, it has been shown that the whole concept is viable and possible to replicate. First, the novel stormwater basin management has demonstrated the potential reuse of relatively large volumes of water. However, reusing the retained water was not yet possible due to weather conditions. Real-life reuse scenarios are needed to get a more exact view on the potential water reuse. Second, the potential of subirrigation as an additional water source to crops in dry periods was shown in a test set up before the basin was built. During this test, water was taken up by crops through capillary rise. Hence, it can be concluded that the reused water fed through subirrigation can form a supplementary water source for irrigation during dry periods, hereby (slightly) lowering water demand from other sources like tap water and groundwater.

Water quality was followed up throughout the project. A sand filter was installed between the buffer basin and the subirrigation to ensure water fed to the subirrigation would not deteriorate the soil and groundwater quality. The sand filter had limited added value due to a decent initial water quality and a limited removal rate. Therefore, it is questionable whether the investment and operational costs of the treatment are justifiable within the overall concept. Good communication with the end user and pragmatic evaluation in comparison with other, generally used, water sources is recommended. Water quality did not always comply to the EQS for groundwater. In the current study, the identified exceedances are evaluated to be of minor risk in relation to other legislator frameworks, such as the background concentrations of groundwater, the tipping point for water/fertilizer and the drinking water directive. Nevertheless, given the direct impact of subirrigation on the groundwater system, water quality should be monitored on the longer term to avoid the potential risk of the subirrigation water affecting groundwater and soil quality in the future. A monitoring protocol to this end has been proposed. Besides, groundwater protection, clogging of the drainage pipes is an additional point of attention based on the identified water quality.

Main concerns regarding the stormwater reuse, particular to the Mechelen case, involve ownership. As farmers cannot rely on water availability in the buffer basin for water supply for their crops, their willingness to pay is limited. Moreover, the biggest beneficiaries are the environment and citizens and industry that would suffer occasional flooding if the buffer basin would not have been built. Unfortunately, there is no clear model to get funds from the latter group in this case. Hence, finding a source to cover the operational costs is not clear.

Concerns regarding the concept of coupling subirrigation to a buffer basin in a smart way relate to the legal framework. Creating a legal framework taking necessary precautions for potential risks, with

respect to e.g. water quality, while keeping realization of similar projects realistic and workable is necessary.

Finally, the experiences during this project demonstrate the viability of the concept presented. Nevertheless, each situation where this concept can be applied will be different with regard to the geohydrological conditions, the risks for the groundwater system, etc. Hence a tailored approach is needed for each replication. The design of the various components in a modular fashion simplifies this customization process.

7 References

Disclaimer: Language and grammar of single sentences and words in the report were optimized by means of ChatGPT. The authors take full responsibility for the content.

Adriaens, A., Vandendriessche, S., De Coninck, M., Huits, D., Boeckaert, C., Bamelis, L., Meers, E. (2022). Brochure Waterketen. Nutricycle Vlaanderen, Gent.

Agentschap Landbouw & Zeevisserij. (s.d.). *Kwaliteitseisen voor irrigatiewater*. Vlaanderen. <https://lv.vlaanderen.be/voorlichting-info/publicaties/praktijkgidsen/water/duurzaam-watergebruik-de-openluchtgroenteteelt-3>.

Agentschap Zorg en Gezondheid. (29/03/2022). *Actuele no regret zones (PFAS) (EPSPG:31370)* [Database]. Ondersteunend Centrum Databank Ondergrond Vlaanderen. <https://www.vlaanderen.be/datavindplaats/catalogus/actuele-no-regret-zones-pfas>.

BOSAQ. (2023). *Aquafin - SF-(AC-UV) pilot B-watersmart - Functional description*. Deinze.

Butler, D. and Davies, J. W. (2004) *Urban drainage*, London; New York, Spon Press. [online] <http://search.ebscohost.com/login.aspx?direct=true&scope=site&db=nlebk&db=nlabk&AN=116885> (Accessed May 16, 2022).

Coördinatiecommissie Integraal Waterbeleid (2012). *Code of good practice for the design, construction and maintenance of sewer systems (Code van goede praktijk voor het ontwerp, de aanleg en het onderhoud van rioleringsystemen)*, Erembodegem, Belgium, Coördinatiecommissie Integraal Waterbeleid, Erembodegem, Belgium. (in Dutch) [online] <http://www.integraalwaterbeleid.be/nl/publicaties/code-goede-praktijk-rioleringsystemen/Code%20Van%20Goede%20Praktijk%20Rioleringsystemen.pdf>.

Coördinatiecommissie Integraal Waterbeleid. (20/03/2024). Technisch achtergronddocument bij de gewestelijke stedenbouwkundige verordening hemelwater. D/2024/6871/009, Coördinatiecommissie Integraal Waterbeleid, Aalst.

Tang, D.W.S., Van der Zee, S.E.A.T.M., Narain-ford, D.M., van den Eertwegh, G.A.P.H., Bartholomeus, R.P. (2023). Managed phreatic zone recharge for irrigation and wastewater treatment. *Journal of Hydrology*, 626 (part A). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2023.130208>.

De Buyck, P.J., Van Hulle, S.W.H., Dumoulin, A. et al. Roof runoff contamination: a review on pollutant nature, material leaching and deposition. *Rev Environ Sci Biotechnol*, 20, 549–606 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11157-021-09567-z>.

de Wit, J. A., Ritsema, C. J., van Dam, J. C., van den Eertwegh, G. A. P. H., Bartholomeus, R. P. (2022). Development of subsurface drainage systems: Discharge – retention – recharge. *Agricultural Water Management*, 269. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agwat.2022.107677>

de Wit, J.A., van der Schans, M.L., van Loon, A.H., Cirkel, D.G., van den Eertwegh, G.A.P.H., Bartholomeus, R.P. (2023). Verstopping voorkomen bij regelbare drainage met subirrigatie op hoge zandgronden - Evaluatie van veld- en kolomproeven in America, Stegeren, Lieshout en Haaksbergen. KWR 2023.085, KWR, Nieuwegein.

de Wit, J.A., van Huijgevoort, M.H.J., van Dam, J.C., van den Eertwegh, G.A.P.H., van Dejl, D., Ritsema, C.J., Bartholomeus, R. (2024). Hydrological consequences of controlled drainage with subirrigation. *Journal of Hydrology*, 628. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2023.130432>.

Elsen, F., Janssens, P., Meuris, S. (23 december 2020). Kansen voor subirrigatie. *Boer & Tuinder*, 23 december 2020, 42 - 44.

Kuzma, S., Saccoccia, L., Chertock, M. (16 August 2023). *25 Countries, Housing One-quarter of the Population, Face Extremely High Water Stress*. World Resources Institute. <https://www.wri.org/insights/highest-water-stressed-countries>.

Narain-Ford, D.M., Bartholomeus, R.P., Dekker, S.C., van Wezel, A.P. (2020). Natural Purification Through Soils: Risks and Opportunities of Sewage Effluent Reuse in Sub-surface Irrigation. *Reviews of Environmental Contamination and Toxicology*, 250, pp 85–117. https://doi.org/10.1007/398_2020_49.

Narain-Ford, D.M., van Wezel, A.P., Helmus, R., Dekker, S.C., Bartholomeus, R.P. (2022). Soil self-cleaning capacity: Removal of organic compounds during sub-surface irrigation with sewage effluent. *Water Research*, 266. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2022.119303>.

Regulation (EU) 2020/741 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 May 2020 on minimum requirements for water reuse. *Official Journal of the European Union (L177)*, 05.06.2020, 32 - 55.

Directive (EU) 2020/2184 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 December 2020 on the quality of water intended for human consumption (recast). *Official Journal of the European Union (L435)*, 23.12.2020, 1 – 62.

Municipal technology branch US EPA. (September 1999). Storm Water - Technology Fact Sheet - Sand Filters. EPA 832-F-99-007, US EPA, Washington D.C.

Titel II van het VLAREM. Besluit van de Vlaamse regering van 1 juni 1995 houdende algemene en sectorale bepalingen inzake milieuhygiëne. (03/07/2024). <https://navigator.emis.vito.be/detail?wold=263&woLang=nl&woVersion=2024-07-03>.

Titel II van het VLAREM. Besluit van de Vlaamse regering van 1 juni 1995 houdende algemene en sectorale bepalingen inzake milieuhygiëne. (06/10/2024). <https://navigator.emis.vito.be/detail?wold=19128&woLang=nl&woVersion=2024-10-06>

Titel II van het VLAREM – bijlagen. Besluit van de Vlaamse regering van 1 juni 1995 houdende algemene en sectorale bepalingen inzake milieuhygiëne. (03/07/2024). <https://navigator.emis.vito.be/detail?wold=17775&woLang=nl&woVersion=2024-07-03>.

Vlaanderen (s.d.). *Erkende rampen sinds 2014*. Vlaanderen. <https://www.vlaanderen.be/natuur-milieu-en-klimaat/schadevergoeding-vlaams-rampenfonds-aanvragen/erkende-rampen-sinds-2014>.

VITO. (February 2010). *Sand filtration*. <https://emis.vito.be/en/node/22621>.

Willems, P. (02/06/2023). *Vlaanderen heeft een hoge kwetsbaarheid voor droogte*. KULeuven. <https://www.kuleuven.be/duurzaamheid/vk-tegelwippen/water-waterinfiltratie/vlaanderen-heeft-een-hoge-kwetsbaarheid-voor-droogte>.

Annexes

Annex 1 Overview of quality results

Table 3: Mean and maximum concentrations of various pollutants analyzed in the stormwater and the outlet of the sand filter. Including the percentage of results that is above LOQ and some relevant guidelines.

Parameter	Group	Unit	Run-off water 2023 - 2024			Outlet SF			Guidelines for irrigation water quality (Agentschap Landbouw & Zeevisserij, s.d.)	EQS groundwater (Titel II van het VLAREM - bijlagen, versie van 03/07/2024, Bijlage 2.4.1)	Recommended values for subirrigation (de Wit et al., 2023)	Tipping point fertilizer/water (Adriaens et al., 2022)
			Mean	Max	%>LOQ	Mean	Max	%>LOQ				
Arsenic	Metal	mg/L	0.0026	0.004	78.6	0.0023	0.0031	60		0.020 (mg/L)		
Cadmium	Metal	mg/L	0.01	0.01	0	0.01	0.01	0		0.005 (mg/L)		
Chromium	Metal	mg/L	0.015	0.015	0	0.015	0.015	0		0.050 (mg/L)		
Copper	Metal	mg/L	0.016	0.022	28.6	0.015	0.016	10	0.06-0.2 (mg/l)	0.1 (mg/L)		
Iron	Metal	mg/L	1.5	3.3	100	1.13	2.48	100	1.1-1.7 (mg/l)	20 (mg/L)	0.01 (mg/L)	
Lead	Metal	mg/L	0.015	0.015	0	0.015	0.015	0		0.020 (mg/L)		
Mercury	Metal	mg/L	0.0003	0.0003	0	0.0003	0.0003	0		0.001 (mg/L)		
Nickel	Metal	mg/L	0.015	0.015	0	0.015	0.015	0		0.040 (mg/L)		
Zinc	Metal	mg/L	0.058	0.166	100	0.033	0.055	80	0.2-0.7 (mg/l)	0.5 (mg/L)		

Parameter	Group	Unit	Run-off water 2023 - 2024			Outlet SF			Guidelines for irrigation water quality (Agentschap Landbouw & Zeevisserij, s.d.)	EQS grondwater (Titel II van het VLAREM - bijlagen, versie van 03/07/2024, Bijlage 2.4.1)	Recommended values for subirrigation (de Wit et al., 2023)	Tipping point fertilizer/water (Adriaens et al., 2022)
			Mean	Max	%>LOQ	Mean	Max	%>LOQ				
Ammonium	Nutrient	mg N/L	0.5	0.9	100	0.5	0.9	100	0.5 (mg/L) (=0.39 mgN/L) background-concentration = 4.6 mg/L (= 3.58 mg N/L)			
Kjeldahl nitrogen			1.9	4	100	1.69	2.7	100				
Nitrate	Nutrient	mg N/L	1.7	3.3	100	1.5	2.3	100	50 (mg/L) (=11.3 mgN/L)			
Nitrite			0.07	0.13	100	0.079	0.14	100				
Orthophosphate	Nutrient	mg P/L	0.3	0.7	84.6	0.3	0.6	77.8	1.34 (mg/L) (=0.44 mgP/L)			
Oxidized nitrogen (NO ₂ + NO ₃)			1.75	3.4	100	1.52	2.4	100				
Total nitrogen	Nutrient	mg N/L	3.7	5.5	100	3.21	4.1	100			15 (mg N/L)	
Total phosphorus			0.6	1	100	0.5	0.7	100			2 (mg P/L)	

Parameter	Group	Unit	Run-off water 2023 - 2024			Outlet SF			Guidelines for irrigation water quality (Agentschap Landbouw & Zeevisserij, s.d.)	EQS grondwater (Titel II van het VLAREM - bijlagen, versie van 03/07/2024, Bijlage 2.4.1)	Recommended values for subirrigation (de Wit et al., 2023)	Tipping point fertilizer/water (Adriaens et al., 2022)
			Mean	Max	%>LOQ	Mean	Max	%>LOQ				
Biochemical oxygen demand	Organic	mg O2/L	4	7	69.2	4	6	66.7				
Chemical oxygen demand	Organic	mg O2/L	41	52	100	37	44	100		DOC < 2 (mg/L) AOC < 10 (µg/L)		
Mineral oils	Organic	mg/L	0.06	0.1	15.4	0.06	0.1	0	0.010 (mg/L)			
pH	Organic		7.8	8.7	100	7.8	8.1	100	5 - 8.5			
Suspended solids	Organic	mg/L	16	30	100	10	37	100		0.1 (mg/L)		
UV 254 absorbance	Organic		0.525	0.827	100	0.476	0.759	100				
UV 254 absorbance after filtration	Organic		0.388	0.583	100	0.344	0.583	100				
UV 254 transmittance	Organic	%	28.7	46.1	100	30.6	47.9	100				
UV 254 transmittance after filtration	Organic	%	36.9	51.3	100	37.5	56.8	100				

Parameter	Group	Unit	Run-off water 2023 - 2024			Outlet SF			Guidelines for irrigation water quality (Agentschap Landbouw & Zeevisserij, s.d.)	EQS grondwater (Titel II van het VLAREM - bijlagen, versie van 03/07/2024, Bijlage 2.4.1)	Recommended values for subirrigation (de Wit et al., 2023)	Tipping point fertilizer/water (Adriaens et al., 2022)
			Mean	Max	%>LOQ	Mean	Max	%>LOQ				
Acenaphtene	PAH	µg/L	0.011	0.022	7.7	0.01	0.01	0				
Acenaphtylene	PAH	µg/L	0.03	0.03	0	0.03	0.03	0				
Anthracene	PAH	µg/L	0.01	0.01	0	0.01	0.01	0				
Benz(a)anthracene	PAH	µg/L	0.010	0.012	7.7	0.01	0.01	0				
Benzo(a)pyrene	PAH	µg/L	0.011	0.021	7.7	0.01	0.01	0				
Benzo(b)fluoranthene	PAH	µg/L	0.011	0.024	15.4	0.01	0.01	0				
Benzo(g,h,i)perylene	PAH	µg/L	0.012	0.029	15.4	0.01	0.01	0				
Benzo(k)fluoranthene	PAH	µg/L	0.01	0.01	0	0.01	0.01	0				
Chrysene	PAH	µg/L	0.010	0.014	15.4	0.01	0.01	0				
Dibenz(a,h)anthracene	PAH	µg/L	0.01	0.01	0	0.01	0.01	0				
Fluoranthene	PAH	µg/L	0.014	0.027	38.5	0.01	0.01	0				
Fluorene	PAH	µg/L	0.011	0.019	7.7	0.01	0.01	0				
Indeno(1,2,3-c,d)pyrene	PAH	µg/L	0.011	0.024	7.7	0.01	0.01	0				
Naphtalene	PAH	µg/L	0.024	0.047	15.4	0.02	0.02	0				
Phenanthrene	PAH	µg/L	0.012	0.021	38.5	0.01	0.01	0				
Pyrene	PAH	µg/L	0.013	0.025	30.8	0.01	0.01	11.1				
Sum of 16 PAHs	PAH	µg/L	0.145	0.19	46.2	0.17	0.19	11.1		0.2 (mg/L)		
Sum of 6 PAHs	PAH	µg/L	0.074	0.19	38.5	0.06	0.06	0				

Parameter	Group	Unit	Run-off water 2023 - 2024			Outlet SF			Guidelines for irrigation water quality (Agentschap Landbouw & Zeevisserij, s.d.)	EQS grondwater (Titel II van het VLAREM - bijlagen, versie van 03/07/2024, Bijlage 2.4.1)	Recommended values for subirrigation (de Wit et al., 2023)	Tipping point fertilizer/water (Adriaens et al., 2022)
			Mean	Max	%>LOQ	Mean	Max	%>LOQ				
Calcium	Salt	mg/L	73.6	95.1	100	73.6	94.9	100	120 (mg/l)	270 (mg/L)	SI_Ca < 0.5	
Chloride	Salt	mg/L	59	168	100	66	168	100	50-100 (mg/l)	250 (mg/L)		
Conductivity	Salt	µS/cm	622	980	100	626	974	100	0.8-1.5 (mS/cm)	1600 (µS/cm)		
Magnesium	Salt	mg/L	7.1	10.1	100	7.0	10.1	100	25 (mg/l)	20 (mg/L) (Background- concentration = 23 mg/L)		
Potassium	Salt	mg/L	11.8	17.7	100	21.7	115	100				
Sodium	Salt	mg/L	34.5	98.6	100	38.3	94.9	100	30-60 (mg/l)	150 (mg/L)		
Sulfate	Salt	mg/L	43.5	88	100	38.2	48	100				

Annex 2 Compounds to be monitored for Managed Aquifer Recharge according to VLAREM II

Table 4: Compounds to be measured yearly

Anions: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sulphate - Chloride - Carbonate - Bicarbonate 	Cations: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Calcium - Potassium - Sodium - Magnesium
Unwanted compounds: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Nitrite - Nitrate - Ammonium - Fluoride - Manganese 	BTEX: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Benzene - Toluene - Ethylbenzene - Xylene
metals: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lead - Zinc - Cadmium - Copper - Nickel - Arsenic - Kwik - Chromium 3+ - Total Iron 	VOCI <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1,2-dichloorethane - Dichloormethane - Tetrachloormethane - Tetrachloorethene - Trichloromethanene - Trichloorethene - 1,1,1-trichloorethane - 1,1,2-trichloorethane - 1,1- dichloorethane - cis-1,2-dichloorethene - trans-1,2-dichloorethene
Pesticides: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Total - individual 	
Mineral oil	Vinyl chloride

